

Optimization of a chemical bath for blackening of a grade of steel useful for construction of vision instruments

Lakhi Ram Chauhan*, Kshipra Misra^a, J. K. Bajpai, Majar Singh and Rohit Makan

Instruments Research & Development Establishment (IRDE), DRDO, Dehradun-248 008, Uttarakhand, India

E-mail: lrchauhan@irde.drdo.in

^aDefence Institute of Physiology & Allied Sciences (DIPAS), DRDO, Delhi-110 054, India

Manuscript received 24 November 2017, revised 26 April 2018, accepted 28 April 2018

This work is an extension of our earlier development work. A chemical bath developed for optical coating on a particular kind of stainless steel, is utilized for the blackening of selected steel used for the fabrication of specific mechanical components for the vision instruments. In this study, first operating parameters of the formulated bath is evaluated and then the process is optimized for desired black oxide coating on the surface of this specified steel. Characterization of coating for optical and mechanical properties (hardness and roughness), surface micro-structure and environmental effect is carried out by using spectroscopy, indentation hardness test, optical profilometer, SEM, sea-water immersion and temperature variation test methods.

Keywords: Steel, chemical bath, black coating, characterization.

Introduction

Iron is the metal of choice for many items because of its strength and abundance. However pure iron is seldom used. The main application areas of iron alloys are: structural, automotive, marine, defence, consumer products¹. There are three main commercial forms of iron: cast iron (2–3% carbon), wrought iron (0.12–0.25% carbon) and steel (0.25–2% carbon). Out of these three forms, steel possesses good mechanical and corrosion resistant properties, hence it is a most important engineering material. There are two main categories of steel:

(i) Plain carbon steel

e.g. Mild steel (<0.5% carbon), Hard steel (>0.5% carbon)

(ii) Alloy steel

e.g. Stainless steel, Chrome steel, Nickel steel, Manganese steel

Selection of the steel depends on the intended applications. Manganese steel is hard, tough and resistant to wear compared to other alloy steels. This kind of steel is generally used for fabrication of rock

crushing machinery, safes, railway tracks etc.^{2,3}.

Vision instruments are sighting tools made using sophisticated optical glasses and electronic components. During the development of these instruments mechanical components such as casing, housing, mount, holder, clamp, cabinetry etc. are required. The desirable materials of construction (MoC) for these components include alloys of aluminum, magnesium, copper and iron. Manganese steel is found suitable for the fabrication of a few of these components for specific purposes because of its very good mechanical properties.

Surface finishing is a very important treatment for the fabricated component to control the environmental effects and appearance. An important consideration in the design and construction of vision instruments is the minimization of stray and scattered light within the instrument. The wavelength range $250 < \lambda < 2500$ nm is of interest to optical and infrared instruments in the ultraviolet, visible, and near-infrared regimes⁴. Black oxide coatings are a known class of finishes to accomplish this require-

ment. There are many surface blackening processes for ferrous metals given in the literature⁵. It has been found, however, that the process developed for one grade of steel to produce the desired coating is not suitable for the other grade.

In this study the prospect of a chemical bath developed in our previous work for the blackening of stainless steel is extended for a grade of steel. This specific type of steel is found suitable for the fabrication of some specific mechanical components for the Vision Instruments. The process is evaluated with the help of literatures⁶ and conducting several sets of experiments. In this evaluation this chemical bath is also found suitable for blackening of selected steel. The desired black oxide coating on the surface of steel is obtained by changes in the evaluated operating parameters. The operating temperature of previous set-up was 135°C ($\pm 5^\circ\text{C}$) and immersion time period was 45 min. The possible reaction steps responsible for black coating formation during the process are explored and the characterization of the deposited layer is discussed.

Experimental

Preparation of sample:

A test steel sample containing elements as per given in Table 1 of size ($4 \times 2 \times 0.1$) cm³ is cut for the experimental work. The sample is then mechanically mirror polished using international quality standard polishing paper⁷. In this work silicon carbide (SiC) abrasive papers of 320, 400, and 500 grit (CAMI designation) are used to get mirror-polished surface. After this sample is water ringed, then washed with distilled water and then cleaned in acetone and finally dried in an oven at 100°C for 10 min. An image of the sample prepared by this process is shown in Fig. 1A.

Chemical composition of test steel sample is estimated using XRF-analyzer (M/s Olympus, USA make).

Table 1. Elemental composition of steel sample

Elements	P	Si	Mn	Fe
% (Wt)	0.034	0.206	0.35	99.33

Fig. 1. Sample (A) before and (B) after coating.

Preparation of bath:

The bath is formulated as per our previously developed bath by adding 800 g of sodium hydroxide (NaOH), 100 g of sodium nitrite (NaNO₂), 300 g of chromium trioxide (CrO₃) and 1000 ml of double-distilled water in a SS-pot of 1.5 liter capacity. The bath solution is stirred gently till all substances are mixed. Specific gravity (or relative density) and pH of the prepared solution are recorded as 1.600 and 14, respectively, at room temperature (27°C).

Coating process:

300 ml of bath solution is taken in a 500 ml SS-bath. The bath is then kept on a suitable heating plate (Model No. C-MAG HS7, IKA German make) and heated up to 125°C. Now the prepared sample is immersed in the bath. The bath temperature is maintained at 125°C ($\pm 5^\circ\text{C}$) for 30 min and the bath solution is agitated every 10 min during this period.

Rate of deposition and dissolution:

In this evaluation three samples of different sizes are prepared as per the above procedure and weighed. Then the samples are coated using above technique and weighed again to see the mass variation.

Surface morphology:

Surface morphology affects several functional attributes of parts, such as friction, wear, lubrication, light reflection, heat transmission, coating etc. Hence, the inspection of surface micro-structure of the work piece is very important to assess the quality of a component^{8,9}.

Two samples of size ($2 \times 2 \times 0.1$) cm³, one uncoated and another coated are prepared by above processes. The surface micro-structural of the test samples is then analyzed using Scanning Electron

Chauhan *et al.*: Optimization of a chemical bath for blackening of a grade of steel useful *etc.*

Microscope (SEM) (M/s Carl Zeiss Microscopy Ltd., Germany). Surface roughness of the samples is measured using Optical Surface Profilometer (M/s Bruker GT-1, USA make).

Measurement of optical character:

Spectrophotometers are used to characterize optical properties such as reflectance/absorption, and transmittance/opaqueness of a sample. To evaluate optical property of the surface, two samples of same size (dimensions $2 \times 2 \times 0.1 \text{ cm}^3$), one un-coated and one coated, are prepared as per above techniques. Then the surface reflectance of the both samples is recorded in visible and near IR regions¹⁹. A Double Beam Spectrophotometer (M/s Perkin-Elmer's Lamda-950) is used to record reflection curves.

Immersion test:

Corrosion resistance behavior of the coating under sea-water is evaluated using synthetic sea-water. Artificial (synthetic) sea water is prepared as per IS: 10236. Two test samples of the same size ($1 \times 1 \times 0.1 \text{ cm}^3$), one un-coated and one coated, are prepared as per above methods. The samples are then weighed and immersed into 100 ml of artificial sea-water. After 5-days, 10-days and 15-days immersion time period, samples are cleaned and dried gently and then visually inspected and weighed¹⁰⁻¹². Sea-water is changed after every five days immersion period.

Study of temperature variation effects:

For study of temperature variation effect on coating, two coated samples having dimensions of $7 \times 3 \times 0.1 \text{ cm}^3$ are prepared. Then from these, one sample is exposed to hot environment (500°C) and one to cold environment (-15°C). Temperature variation resistance coating is useful for space, cryogenic storage, military and energy conversion applications^{13,14}.

Surface hardness measurement:

Micro-hardness difference between the coated and un-coated surfaces is assessed by using Nano Test Vantage, indentation hardness testing machine (M/s Micro-Materials, UK make).

Results and discussion

Bath and process:

Formation of blackish surface is seen after exposures of the sample for 10 min. Desired black color and uniform coating is observed after 30 min of treatment. The optimized compositions of bath and operating temperature are given in Table 2.

Table 2. Optimized chemical blackening process for steel substrate

Bath compositions	Operating parameters
800 g of NaOH + 100 g of NaNO ₂ + 300 g of CrO ₃ + 1000 ml of H ₂ O	Temp.: 125°C (±5°C) Time: 30 min

From above experimental studies it is revealed that the bath developed during our previous study is also found suitable for blackening of this particular steel after minor changes in operating parameters.

Black finish obtained consists of a mixture of the oxides of iron; ferric and ferrous oxide sometimes called ferric-ferroso oxide or magnetite. This oxide is produced by the conversion of the iron metal into the oxide. The possible reaction mechanism to form thin Fe₃O₄ film on steel substrate can be described as follows¹⁵⁻¹⁸:

It is also found during this evaluation that the bath performance was constant for a long period. As per our records in using the bath for two years, no significant adverse or alteration effect was observed. Long period bath performance is evaluated by measuring the pH and specific gravity after maintaining volume. pH and specific gravity of the bath are recorded ~14 and ~1.600 respectively during this period, these figures are same as measured in beginning.

Deposition and dissolution rate:

It is observed that sample weight is decreased after the coating process (Table 3). It shows that, the

Table 3. Test samples weight variations after the treatment process

Sl. No.	Wt. g (A) (before treatment)	Wt. g (B) (after treatment)	Wt. g (A ~ B)
1.	1.5809	1.5804	0.0005
2.	1.6068	1.6064	0.0004
3.	20.1207	20.1150	0.0057

weight of deposition is lesser than the weight of removal of the materials on the sample surface.

Surface morphology:

Findings of the surface morphology analyzed by SEM and Optical Profilometer are as under:

SEM analysis:

Fig. 2, shows the SEM images of the top morphology of the un-coated substrate (A), and coated substrate (B) at the same magnification i.e. 4.96 KX. Both images are clearly different from each other. Image-3A is clear and sharp while image-3B is dull and porous in nature; this is due to the chemical reaction between the bath solution and surface of the substrate. Porous surface enhanced the absorption capacity of the coating¹⁹.

Fig. 2. SEM images of un-coated (A) and coated (B) samples.

Surface roughness:

Fig. 3 and Fig. 4 show the roughness profiles of un-coated and coated surfaces of the steel samples measured by the optical profilometer. Both figures clearly indicate increase in the roughness after coat-

ing. The average roughness (Ra) of the un-coated and coated surfaces of the samples obtained by this method are 62.115 nm and 78.977 nm, respectively. The difference between these two results may be attributed to the absorption and dissolution reactions between the bath solution and surface of the substrate during the coating process.

The SEM analysis reveals that the porosity of the surface increases after the coating; similarly roughness test shows that surface roughness also increases after the coating treatment. Hence both the results agree with each other.

Optical characterization:

Fig. 5 shows the reflectance spectrum of coated (C) and un-coated (UC) samples. It is clear from these curves that after coating, surface reflection reduces more than three times the reflection of un-coated sample. This decrease in reflectance is the combined effect of, increased surface roughness and formation of black oxide layer on the surface after the coating process. Curves also show that reflectance difference in near IR-region is higher than in the visible region.

Sea-water effect:

Fig. 6 shows the images of un-coated (1) and coated (2) samples before immersion, and after 5-days, 10-days, and 15-days salt-water immersion. Visual inspections of the coated samples show that

Fig. 3. Profilographs of un-coated and coated samples.

for up to five days, it is almost protective. After 10-days, more than half of the coating disappears and after 15-days almost the complete layer is removed.

Weight variation of the test samples are noted in Table 4. From this observation it is found that coating is nearly protective for five days. Weight difference of the coated sample is about four times (0.0005 g) less than the un-coated sample (0.0018 g). After 5-days, weight variations of both samples are quite close and after 15-days it is similar. This result is also in agreement with the visual inspection of the test samples.

On the basis of above gravimetric analysis, corrosion rate (CR) in millimeter per year (mm/y) is calculated using following ASTM standard formula:

$$\text{Corrosion rate (mm/y)} = W \times 8.75 \times 10^4 / D \times A \times T$$

where, W = weight loss of the sample (g), D =

Fig. 4. X and Y profiles of un-coated and coated samples.

Fig. 5. Reflectance curves; UC: uncoated and C: coated.

Fig. 6. Un-coated and coated samples: before and after sea-water immersion.

Table 4. Weight variations of un-coated and coated samples after salt-water immersion

Sample type	Before immersion	5-days immersion		10-days immersion		15-days immersion	
	Wt. (g)	Wt. (g)	Wt. (g)	Wt. (g)	Wt. (g)	Wt. (g)	Wt. (g)
	(A)	(B)	(A-B)	(C)	(A-C)	(D)	(A-D)
Un-coated	1.5988	1.5970	0.0018	1.5956	0.0032	1.5940	0.0048
Coated	1.6064	1.6069	0.0005	1.6034	0.0030	1.6016	0.0048

density of steel (g/cc), A = surface area of the specimen (cm²), T = exposure time (days).

Fig. 7. A graph of CR vs time (days) for un-coated (UC) and coated (C) samples.

Fig. 7 indicates that CR of coated sample is very good (~1) up to five days immersion, while in case of un-coated sample the CR is ~4. After 10 days immersion period, CR difference is very less, and after 15-days immersion period CR is same for both samples. This indicates that after coating, sea-water deterioration effect on the surface of sample can be reduce relative to un-coated surface for a short periods.

Temperature variation effects:

The images of the coated sample before and after the treatment at 500°C temperature for 1-h can be seen in Fig. 8A. In this study no significant temperature effect on the coated surface is observed. However, surface of the sample is observed to smoothen after the heat treatment; this may be due to the alteration of surface microstructure at this temperature.

Coating was also found to be un-affected after exposing the sample at -15°C temperature for 100-h (Fig. 8B).

Fig. 8. A – Test samples before and after treatment at 500°C. B – Test samples before and after 25, 50, 75 and 100 days treatment at -15°C.

Hardness analysis of un-coated and coated surfaces:

Hardness (H) is a mechanical property referring to the ratio of the maximum indentation load (P_{max}) and the measured area (A) i.e.

$$H = P_{max}/A$$

Hardness of the materials is extensively characterized by using indentation hardness test²⁰. Depth-sensing indentation tests (e.g. Berkovich and Vickers) are found suitable to determine the hardness of bulk material and thin coatings. Hardness is measured using Berkovich indenter since load-indentation depth curve and hardness are highest for the Berkovich indenter²¹.

The micro-hardness test result showed that after coating, hardness of the surface increases ~1.74635 GPa (Table 5). This increase in hardness is due to the formation of Fe₃O₄ layer on the surface. Hardness of Fe₃O₄ is >5 and hardness of steel <5 on Mohs scale^{22,23}. Elastic and plastic limit of un-coated and coated surfaces measured can be seen in the following load displacement curves (Fig. 9).

Fig. 9. Loading and un-loading curves.

Table 5. Hardness of un-coated and coated samples

Sample types	Hardness (GPa)
Un-coated	3.66764
Coated	5.41399

Conclusions

The chemical bath developed in our earlier work is also found suitable for blackening of this specified grade of steel. This bath can be used for other kinds

of ferrous alloys by adjusting the operating parameters to find the desired black coating. Concluding points extracted from this study can be summarized as following:

Porous, uniform, black oxide coating can be produced using this technique.

Coating is able to reduce reflectance effectively.

Coating is resistive to temperature variations from -15 to 500°C .

Coating exhibits inferior corrosion resistance in sea-water.

Surface hardness and roughness increase after the coating.

Process is simple, cheap and requires moderate operating temperature.

Bath remains stable for long periods (our observation is >2 years).

Acknowledgements

The authors are thankful to Dr. Amit Agarwal for SEM and surface roughness analysis, Mr. Satyendra Kr. Singh for hardness evaluation test and all colleagues of Mechanical Workshop and Chemical Technology Lab for their help to perform the experimental work. They would also like to thank the Vice-Chancellor and RDC members, Uttarakhand Technical University (UTU), Dehradun for providing valuable suggestions periodically. Finally authors also like to thank Mr. Benjamin Lionel Outstanding Scientist and Director, IRDE, for his valuable support, guidance and permission to submit this work for publication.

References

1. Manoj Kumar, Arul Kumar and A. R. Manikandan, *International Journal of Innovative Research in Science, Engineering and Technology*, February 2015, **4**, Special Issue 2.
2. Satish V. Kailas, "Applications and Processing of Metals and Alloys", Chap. 9, Indian Institute of Science, Bangalore, India.
3. Satya Prakash, G. D. Tuli, S. K. Basu and R. D. Madan, "Advanced Inorganic Chemistry", S. Chand & Company (Pvt.) Ltd., New Delhi, India, 1987.

4. J. L. Marshall, P. Williams, J. P. Rheault, T. Prochaska, R. D. Allen and D. L. DePoy, "Characterization of the Reflectivity of Various Black Materials", Department of Physics and Astronomy, TAM University, USA.
5. W. N. Hussein, *Journal of Babylon University/Engineering Sciences*, 2012, **20**.
6. Jing-Yu Chen, Yong-Min Chen, *et al.*, *Ceramics International*, 2014, **40**, 14983.
7. K. H. Orvis and H. D. Grissino-Mayer, *Tree-Ring Resaerch*, 2002, **58(1/2)**, 47.
8. H. Matysiak, R. Haratym, J. Kwapisz and M. Klebczyk, *A.F.E.*, 2011, **11**, 131.
9. V. B. Suryawanshi and K. H. Inamdar, *I.J.E.R.A.*, 2012, **2(3)**, 1512.
10. R. O. Rihan and S. Nestic, *Corrosion Science*, 2006, **48**, 2633.
11. L. R. Chauhan and G. Gunasekaran, *Corrosion Science*, 2006.
12. W. B. James, "Salt spray and immersion corrosion testing of PM Stainless Steel materials", H. Corporation Cinnaminson, NJ, 2011.
13. Veronika Stelmakh *et al.*, *J. Vac. Sci. Tech.*, 2015, **33**, 6.
14. "Inorganic Conversion Coatings for Ferrous Substrates", US 6322898 B1, 2001.
15. L. H. Vagner, "Corrosion resistance of black oxide coating on mild and corrosion resistant steels (Technical Report)", R. I. A. Laboratory, Rack Island, USA, 1964.
16. Shiue *et al.*, USP-6512667 B2, 2003.
17. Menke *et al.*, USP-5104463 A, 1992.
18. R. M. Hurd and N. Hackerman, *J. Electrochem. Soc.*, 1957, **104(8)**, 482.
19. S. Jafari and S. M. Rozati, "World Renewable Energy Congress", Linkoping, Sweden, 2011.
20. Malzbender *et al.*, *Materials Science and Engineering*, 2002, **R-36**, 47.
21. N. A. Sakharova, J. V. Fernandes, J. M. Antunes and M. C. Oliveira, *International Journal of Solids and Structures*, 2009, **46**, 1095.
22. https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Mohs_scale_of_mineral_hardness.
23. <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Magnetite>.